

Preliminary Study for Multi-objective Core Design Optimization Using Bayesian Optimization

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ABSTRACT

The Japan Atomic Energy Agency has been developing an integrated evaluation system for advanced reactors such as fast reactors, known as Advanced Reactor Knowledge- and AI-aided Design Integration Approach through the whole plant lifecycle (ARKADIA). ARKADIA seeks to accelerate the process from innovative reactor design to social implementation. Within this framework, an optimization process for reactor core design is under development. This optimization process involves the integrated sequential analyses of neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel integrity evaluation, which previously were conducted separately, using a Bayesian optimization algorithm to automatically calculate the optimal design variables that maximize core performance. Thereby, considerable reduction in human resources and time costs can be achieved. Development has progressed in stages. In previous studies, focus was given to single-objective optimization problems of core design, and optimal solutions consistent with the reference solutions were obtained. Herein, to provide more flexible design options, the scope was extended to multi-objective optimization (MOO). A MOO problem with seven variables was set, and applicability of the optimization process was examined. In addition, a correlation analysis tool for the obtained Pareto solutions was developed in order to analyze the results of multi-objective optimization in detail. A demonstration of this tool was also performed. As a result, Pareto solutions for the set MOO problem could be obtained. The correlation analysis tool could quantify correlations among multiple design variables and core characteristics. Thereby, an all-encompassing analysis of complex correlations in core design could be realized.

Keywords: Sodium-cooled fast reactor, Core design, Multi-objective optimization, Pareto solutions, Correlation analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) has been developing an innovative evaluation system assisted by artificial intelligence (AI) and state-of-the-art analysis and evaluation methods, known as Advanced Reactor Knowledge- and AI-aided Design Integration Approach through the whole plant lifecycle (ARKADIA) [1]. ARKADIA aims to support innovative core designs from the viewpoint of safety, economy, and sustainability as a carbon-free energy source by integrating AI, related state-of-the-art technologies, and knowledge accumulated through past research/development for innovative reactors such as sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFR). Consequently, the process from innovative reactor design to social implementation can be accelerated.

Under this project, an optimization process for core design is being developed. In the conventional core design process, neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, fuel integrity evaluation and plant dynamics are

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individually conducted based on the boundary conditions set between the analyses and processing abundant data. If the evaluation results do not satisfy the requirements, the design parameters are adjusted or the boundary conditions are re-considered, and each analysis must be re-performed, which is a time-consuming process. Such a core design may take several months to a year. To address this issue, an optimization process, which combines an optimization algorithm with the integrated sequential analyses of neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, fuel integrity evaluation and plant dynamics, is being developed and obtains design variables that maximize the specified core performance (objective function). The optimization process enables a significant reduction in the time required for core design and automatically provides optimal design variables to the designers. A representative core design optimization problem (16-variable, 12-constraint, four-objective optimization problem [2]) was identified and solving the representative problem was set as the first milestone in development. Bayesian optimization (BO) [3] has great global search capability and efficiency, and has been assessed as a candidate for the optimization algorithm. We have been gradually advancing development, checking performance with a simplified version of the representative problem. Initially, a toy model of the reactor core was used to confirm that optimal solutions consistent with the reference solutions could be derived for single-objective and two-objective optimization problems with two variables, targeting only neutronic analysis [4]. Using the toy model, a prototype of a neutronic-plant dynamics sequential analyses function was developed, and feasibility of the optimization calculation which combines the sequential analyses and BO, could be confirmed [5]. Subsequently, the target was extended to an actual core model, the number of design variables was increased to four, and a single-objective optimization solution, which included sequential analyses of neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel integrity evaluations, could be obtained [2].

Herein, the scope was further extended from single-objective optimization to multi-objective optimization (MOO) problem in order to provide more flexible design options that consider the trade-offs between multiple objective functions. A MOO problem was set, and the optimization process was applied to obtain a solution. Furthermore, a correlation analysis function was developed for the Pareto solutions obtained by solving the MOO problem. Using this function, correlation between objective functions and design variables was analyzed, and a detailed understanding of the results of the MOO could be provided. A demonstration of this function was also performed.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Overview of Multi-objective Bayesian Optimization

In BO, Gaussian process regression (GPR) [6] is used to predict the shape of the objective function, and an optimal solution is sought based on this prediction. GPR predicts a function by the posterior mean and the posterior uncertainty from the given sampling points. Here, given a new point $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and the corresponding $f(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ for the previously obtained training data $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n\}$ and $f(\mathbf{X}) = \{f(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_n)\}$, the joint Gaussianity of all finite subsets is obtained and the prediction is updated. The updated prediction is known as the posterior belief (denoted as $p(f(\hat{\mathbf{x}})|\hat{\mathbf{x}}, \mathbf{X}, f(\mathbf{X}))$). By repeatedly adding new training data and updating the posterior belief, prediction accuracy can be improved (for a more detailed description of GPR, see Ref. [6]). In the BO process, initial sampling is first performed, and the shape of the objective function is predicted from these data using GPR. Then, using a function called the acquisition function, the next search point is determined, and data from the point is acquired to update the posterior distribution. This process is repeated in order to achieve the optimal solution. The acquisition function contains two criteria: the region where the optimal solution is predicted to exist according to the information of posterior mean, and the region where the search has not progressed well and the posterior uncertainty is large. Therefore, the search for optimal solution can proceed efficiently while avoiding falling into a local solution.

MOO problem is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \min_x \{f_1(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_n(\mathbf{x})\}, \\ \text{subject to } \mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{U}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is D-dimensional real-valued input, n is the number of objective functions, $f_n(\mathbf{x})$ is n -th objective function, \mathbf{U} is the feasible set defined as $\mathbf{U} = \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^D: a_i \leq x_i \leq b_i\}$, and a_i and b_i are the upper and lower bounds of the i -th variable, respectively. Because multiple objective functions are considered in trade-off relationships, a solution that optimizes all objective functions simultaneously cannot be uniquely determined. Therefore, the aim is to obtain a set of solutions called Pareto solutions. When solving MOO by BO, the acquisition function is defined using an index called "hypervolume (HV)" [7]. HV is defined as the amount of the region delimited by the Pareto solutions-set \mathcal{P} and the reference point \mathbf{r} in the objective function space. HV becomes the area if the objective function space is two-dimensional or the volume if the objective function space is three-dimensional. If a new search point is added and HV increases, it means that the point is a Pareto solution. Therefore, Pareto solutions can be acquired by predicting the shape of the objective function with GPR and searching for the point where HV is expected to increase. Here, an acquisition function called Expected Hypervolume Improvement (EHVI) was used [8, 9].

Rather than using a time-consuming approach to directly implement BO into the optimization system, an open Python library Trieste was used [10]. The default implementation of Trieste (Version 1.1.2) was used for the acquisition function (EHVI) and GPR settings.

2.2. Integrated Sequential Analyses of Neutronics, Thermal-hydraulics, and Fuel Integrity Evaluation

A system for the integrated sequential analyses of neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel integrity evaluation has been developed [2]. Models for neutronic and thermal hydraulic analyses and the computational model of data transfer between these analyses are shown in Fig. 1. The comprehensive and versatile framework MARBLE [11] was used for neutronic calculations. A deterministic method was used to perform the diffusion and perturbation calculations in the two-dimensional R-Z model as shown in Fig. 1 (a). A homogeneous two-region core was targeted. Plutonium (Pu) enrichments in the inner/outer cores were automatically adjusted so that the effective multiplication factor and the ratio of maximum linear heat rate in the inner/outer cores were at unity.

Thermal hydraulic analysis was performed using the subchannel analysis code ASFRE [12], as shown in Fig. 1 (c). A function to convert the power distribution of the two-dimensional R-Z model into pin units for a three-dimensional model (subchannel model) was implemented. If there are 271 fuel pins in the assembly, 19 pin rows are aligned as shown in Fig. 1(c). Therefore, as shown in Fig. 1(b), the region corresponding to one assembly was divided into 19 rings, and power density at the volume center point of each ring was obtained by interpolation of the results of neutronic calculation. These values were passed to each corresponding pin row of the subchannel model. In other words, an approximation, where the same power density value was given to each pin row in the subchannel model, was used. Since the objective of this study was to check the performance of core design optimization process and does not require precise values, using such approximation was sufficient. In the future, a function to automatically determine flow distribution will be implemented. However, this function is currently under development. Consequently, the assembly closest to the core center, where the power density is the highest and most severe, was tentatively targeted. Coolant flow rate was adjusted so that the maximum cladding mid-wall temperature was 700°C. This is a condition applied to the pool-type SFR

developed in Japan (JP-pool SFR) [13], which was used as the reference core in this study. Cladding temperature distribution and pressure drop at the adjusted flow rate were evaluated.

In the fuel integrity evaluation, the cumulative damage fraction (CDF) is calculated from the power density and cladding temperature histories obtained by neutronics and thermal-hydraulic analyses, respectively. CDF is an index value related to cladding creep rupture. When CDF reaches unity, creep rupture occurs. Focusing on the assembly closest to the core center, CDF values of the pins with the most severe irradiation conditions were evaluated. A more detailed description of the integrated sequential analyses system is provided in [2].

Figure 1. Computational models of the transmission of power density in the two-dimensional R-Z model to the subchannel model (slightly modified from the figure used in Ref. [2])

2.3. Core Model

The JP-pool SFR [13] was used as the reference core. In the optimization calculation, design parameters were fixed except for the design variables which are optimized as explained in Sec 2.4. For instance, the core power was fixed at 1765 MWt, fuel exchange batch was at 6, and the number of fuel pins in the assembly at 271. The fuel nuclide composition was transuranium (TRU) fuel after a fast-reactor multi-recycle [13]. The core was assumed to comprise a hexagonal cylindrical assembly with 11 driver fuel layers including 331 assemblies and a radial blanket layer. The driver fuel layers consist of 198 inner core fuel assemblies, 98 outer core fuel assemblies, and 35 control rods. The control rod configuration consists of one rod at the center of the core, eight in the 4th layer, 10 in the 7th layer, and 16 in the 10th layer. Figure 1(a) shows the two-dimensional R-Z model corresponding to the employed core.

2.4. Optimization problem

For this study, a core optimization problem, which is a simplified version of the representative problem [2]: seven variables, seven constraints, and three objectives, was set as shown in Table I. This problem focuses on neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel integrity, excluding plant dynamics analysis. Three objective functions were set from the economic aspect. The constraints were based on previous JP-pool SFR studies (for the background of setting these constraints, see Ref. [13]).

Table I. Optimization problem set in this study

Optimization problem	Item	Unit	Condition
Objective function	Average discharge burnup (BU_{ave}) in the core	GWd/t	Maximize
	Breeding ratio	-	Maximize
	Pu fissile (P_{uf}) mass at BOEC	t	Minimize
Constraint	Maximum fast neutron fluence (MFNF) ($E > 0.1$ MeV)	$\times 10^{23}n/cm^2$	< 5.0
	Maximum linear heat rate (MLHR)	W/cm	< 430
	Burnup reactivity	$\% \Delta k/kk^1$	< 3.0
	Pu enrichment	wt. %	< 30
	Sodium void reactivity (SVR)	\$	< 6.0
	Maximum pressure drop (MPD)	MPa	< 0.2
	CDF	-	< 0.5
Design variable to be optimized	Core height	cm	70 - 100
	Ratio of fuel pin pitch to diameter (P/D)	-	1.10 - 1.15
	Pin diameter	mm	8.0 - 12.0
	Operation cycle length	d	400 - 700
	Thickness of upper axial blanket fuel (ABF)	cm	10 - 70
	Thickness of lower axial blanket fuel (ABF)	cm	10 - 70
	Number of radial blanket fuel (RBF) assembly	-	50 - 200

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The optimization problem represented in Table I was solved using the optimization process. The calculation condition was tentatively set to 70 initial sampling points and 330 BO search points, for a total of 400 points. As a result, 145 Pareto solutions were obtained. The change in HV converged, indicating that the optimization calculation converged. Distribution of the obtained Pareto solutions is shown in Fig. 2. Figures 2(b)-(d) are the distributions of the Pareto solutions in two-dimensional space for each pair of objective function, which are the projections of the three-dimensional distribution in Fig. 2(a) onto each plane. From these figures, the trade-off relationships between objective functions can be observed. Breeding ratio has negative correlations with average discharge burnup (BU_{ave}) and Pu fissile (P_{uf}) mass, indicating that these core characteristics (the other two objective functions) must be compromised when increasing the breeding ratio. On the other hand, positive correlations with BU_{ave} and P_{uf} mass are observed, and improving one tends to improve the other. In this manner, the Pareto solutions contain information on the trade-offs between objective functions. In addition, insights into the correlation among the set objective functions, constraints and design variables, i.e., the result of variable adjustment to minimize the sacrifice of other objective functions when improving one objective function while taking into account the constraints, can be obtained from the Pareto solutions.

(a) three-dimensional objective function space

(b) Puf mass versus BU_{ave}

(c) BU_{ave} versus breeding ratio

(d) Puf mass versus breeding ratio

Figure 2. Result of multi-objective optimization: distribution of pareto solutions

To quantify the information and insights contained in the Pareto solutions and deepen understanding of the results of multi-objective optimization, a function to calculate Spearman's correlation coefficient [14] was incorporated into the optimization process. The Spearman correlation matrix of the obtained Pareto solutions evaluated by this function is shown in Fig. 3. Various information can be derived from this diagram. For instance, the breeding ratio has negative correlation values of -0.91 and -0.67 with BU_{ave} and Puf mass, respectively, which is consistent with the results in Figs. 2 (c) and (d). The correlation values of BU_{ave} with maximum fast neutron fluence, burnup reactivity, and CDF are close to 1 (strong positive correlation), which is compatible with the empirical rules.

On the other hand, the number of radial blanket fuel (RBF) assembly negatively correlates with the breeding ratio. Empirically, increasing the blanket fuels should improve the breeding ratio (positive correlation). However, when looking at the Pareto solutions, where the design variables were adjusted in consideration of various constraints and trade-offs in the objective function, reducing the number of RBF assembly is suggested to improve the breeding ratio. Here, observing column of the breeding ratio shown in Fig. 3, in addition to the thickness of upper/lower axial blanket fuel (ABF), the pin diameter positively correlated with the breeding ratio. Furthermore, pin diameter negatively correlated with the number of RBF assembly. From this, it is estimated that reducing the RBF and thereby allowing room for some constraints, and increasing the pin diameter, an improvement in the breeding ratio can be assumed. Considering the seven constraints and aiming to increase the breeding ratio while minimizing the sacrifice of other objective functions, manually determining the optimal adjustment, i.e., reducing the RBF assembly and increasing the pin diameter, is considered difficult. However, by combining Bayesian optimization and correlation analysis, insights on detailed design variable adjustments that cannot be determined by manual parametric surveys can be obtained.

Figure 4. Spearman correlation matrix of obtained pareto solutions

In summary, the correlation between many design variables and core characteristics, which designers have considered as empirical knowledge when designing cores, could be quantified, and a comprehensive analysis of complex correlations in core design could be realized. Furthermore, performing correlation analysis can improve the understanding and explanation of optimization results as demonstrated above, and prevent conducting core design optimization in a black-box way, such as in situations where it is difficult to understand why or how such an optimal solution is achieved.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A core design optimization process has been developed in stages under the framework of ARKADIA. In this study, the scope of its application could be extended from single-objective optimization to multi-objective optimization. In addition, a function to perform correlation analysis for the obtained Pareto solutions was implemented. A multi-objective optimization problem was set, and assessment of the performance of the optimization process and the correlation analysis function was carried out. As a result, Pareto solutions of the set problem could be obtained. The correlation analysis function could quantitatively and comprehensively provide information on trade-offs between objective functions, and complex correlations for the design variables and core characteristics could be obtained.

In the future, we will develop functions that provide useful information for users to determine the preference solution (the solution selected by the decision maker in consideration of the importance of each objective function, etc.) from the obtained Pareto solutions, such as a function to compare Pareto solutions or to extract a Pareto solution from the weights of each objective function specified by the user.

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